

USA'S TOURISM EXPERIENCE AND ITS ROLE IN THE FIELD OF INTERNATIONAL TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is an industry that has become an economic and financial provider of the entire country. Therefore, the tourism potential of each country is mentioned in harmony with its economy. This article describes in detail the contribution of the United States of America, one of the hegemonic countries of the world, to tourism and the importance of this country in tourism.

US tourism is a recognized leader in the world tourism market. It ranks first in international tourism revenue (\$96.7 billion in 2017), second in tourism spending (\$76.2 billion), and first in international tourist visits. (83.7 million people). The tourism industry plays an important role in the country's economy. In 2013, according to the American Tourism Industry Association, the total income of the American tourism industry in serving domestic and foreign tourists was 500.5 billion. dol. It is more than 7.2 mln. allows to create new jobs. Why are tourists traveling to the country very active in the USA itself? We can find an answer to this by analyzing the main factors that determine the tourist potential of the USA. The USA is a large and diverse country. It lies on a six-hour stem. The USA has its own different climates, natural zones and landscapes.

In the USA, tourists can ski in the mountains, relax on a tropical beach, hike in the forests and prairies and explore the deserts, engage in fishing in the ocean waves or lakes. In it, you can see volcanoes and geysers, huge glaciers, high peaks, cones, bright examples of Indian summer. All this is in one country. Colorado's Grand Canyon and Niagara Falls, the geysers are world-renowned attractions that attract millions of tourists. The country is made up of a network of national nature parks, the total area of which is 32 million hectares. Americans approach their history very carefully. For this reason, they preserve their historical and cultural monuments. In the USA, 50,000 objects of historical value on a national scale are included in the national state register. Of course, historical and cultural monuments are primarily domestic tourism objects, but the symbols of the American nation, the White House, the Statue of Liberty, and Mount Rashmar are the centers of tourists. If for someone Italy is ancient Rome, the birth century, the USA is "Hollywood" and "Disneyland", New York and Las Vegas. Each state, each city of the USA has the greatest influence in the world according to some indicators, which indicates the specialization of local art.

Many cities in the United States host various festivals or sporting events and attract large numbers of tourists. The United States is a developed country that occupies a unique leading position in the world economy. The level of development of productive forces, the structure of the American economy, its scientific and technical potential, and the level of national competitiveness have a strong influence on all world economic relations. Moreover, the American model of economic growth serves as a model for many developed countries. The USA is a great country that historically attracts tourists. The 21st century was a real testing period for the American tourism industry. The events of September 11, 2001 caused a decline in all indicators of tourism activity. After the events in New York, a real boom in the country's tourism market took place. Even when the price of plane tickets was reduced by 50%, Americans were afraid to fly on airplanes. This had a serious impact on the tourism market, companies were created that deliver the customer to any region of the country by car. First of all, these are aimed at businessmen who go on a business trip for company affairs. From 1998 to 2002, business visits, including conferences, fell by 14%. In general, the foreign flow of tourists to the country decreased by 30% compared to September 2000. Shopping (30%), participation in family and public holidays (27%), and recreation in nature (11%) are the most common purposes and activities for American travel. Visitors to museums and historical places make up 8%, galleries and art museums - 2%. Of the vehicles, cars or trailers (784%), only 16% by plane after 9/11. Buses and trains prefer 2% and 1% respectively. California and Florida are the states most visited by tourists in the USA. They are followed by New York, Texas, and Pennsylvania. Inbound tourism. It ranks third after the United States, France and Spain in terms of tourism. Tourism is a village in the world economy economy, industry, transport and other macroeconomic sectors has its rightful place. In world exports, tourism, oil and oil the third place after the export of products and cars occupies. However, at the moment, there are recreation and tourism opportunities This is because it is not used effectively in the Republic of Uzbekistan the state of affairs in the main sectors of the national economy is far behind its indicators.

Although the American continent holds only third rank in world tourist destinations, after Europe and the Asia-Pacific region, tourism in the Americas is nevertheless an important phenomenon, with 210.9 million international arrivals for 2017, representing 16% of world tourist arrivals (UNWTO, 2018). More importantly still, a number of American countries, such as the US1 and Canada, boast highly developed home tourism. This home market is in fact preponderant for some of the more developed and rapidly growing countries like Brazil. Overall, tourist movement has a powerful structural influence on economies, societies and territories throughout the Americas. However, on the scale of the entire continent, the tourist development of areas is, for geo-historical, cultural, economic and political reasons, a patchy, unequal process. The majority of tourist arrivals is concentrated in North America, with 137 million arrivals for 2017, whereas, for the same period, there were only 36.7 million in South America, 26 million in the Caribbean and 11.2 million in Central America. In this geographical imbalance, the US emerges as uncontested leader both for home and international tourism, figuring regularly as the third most visited country in the world, as in 2017, with 76.9 million international visitors (UNWTO, 2018), way ahead of Mexico (39.3 million) and Canada (28.8 million). The most frequented destinations elsewhere on the continent straggle way behind,

with barely more than 6 million international arrivals for Argentina, Brazil, Chile and the Dominican Republic combined. This state of affairs can be attributed in part to the long-standing development of tourism in the US and Canada, where it began in the 1850s, though in Argentina it dates back to the 1880s, but basically it reflects the disparities between countries in levels of economic development and reproduces the habitually observed economic and socio-political North-over-South hegemony. The cumulative effects of tourism are well-known: the richest countries get the most tourists and gain most from tourism's knock-on effects. Thus, the US alone garners the highest tourist revenues in the world, with 1035.7 billion dollars spent in 2017 by both international² and home tourists (US Travel Association, 2018).

Tourism is first and foremost a powerful factor in the transformation of its territories. Throughout the American continent, it is the reason behind historical and contemporary creations of tailor-made facilities, a fact which accounts for the differentiation and diversification of a whole typology of tourist areas. Three dimensions of such processes need particular attention: the conditions surrounding the tourist development of given areas, the long-term processes of developing tourism and the territorial consequences of that development. Discerning the reasons behind the tourist development of areas is a question of analyzing and deconstructing what certain French geographers have called *le moment de lieu*, the time-place factor (Equipe MIT, 2005). When new places emerge on the tourism planisphere, the explanation habitually brings into play evolutions in cultural representations, inventions and successes in tourist practice and increases in purchasing power. Hervé Théry here demonstrates the role played in Brazil by the growth of the middle class under the Lula government in the formation of a powerful tourist trade in which home tourism is preponderant. The consolidation of two major destinations, the Nordeste and the Sao Paulo region, derives from the proximity of tourist basins with a population of increasing means and from the construction of a social "desire" for vacationing. More rarely invoked, climate change is also driving the emergence of new destinations where new accessibility is opening up pioneer tourist fronts. Alain Grenier describes how global warming and the melting of Arctic ice in Canada have led to the development of polar cruises where rich tourists reactivate dreams of unreachable frontiers. This new adventure tourism throws up a paradox: on the one hand, new world shipping routes upend world geopolitics, on the other, the economic opening of Inuit territory increases the need for the patrimonial protection of the Inuit population and for their participation. Concerning the role of representations in tourist development, Serge Jaumain provides a study of the presentation of the history of Quebec in tourist guides produced since the 1960s. The tourist guide reveals the shifting representations of a territory and mirrors its social, cultural and political transformations. Anglophone and francophone guides of Quebec bear witness to the progressive revalorization of indigenous populations and to the increasing degree of politicization in the presentation of the nation's history. All tourists coming to the USA do not leave the country without visiting New York, the main gate of the country. New York is the tourist capital of the USA. Here is the moment of freedom, the skyscrapers of Manhattan: the Empire State Building, Destroyed by Chrysler-Billing and 9/11. The twin towers of the World Trade Center are located. Hence freedom security measures for tourist visits to the monument and some high towers is

prohibited as However, these cases of New York tourists are world tourism could not damage his reputation in the center. New York has received the status of a world city, national and international headquarters apartment center of corporations, to negotiate employment serves as a public space. In addition, there is an obzor - excursion and cultural and historical tourism is well developed. New York is the country's most famous museums - Metropolitan and Guggenheim. Ethnicity of the city quarters: Little Italy, CHina-Gaumlar are also of great interest to tourists. The UN building is also located in New York.

The advantages of tourism go beyond creating billions of dollars and hundreds of millions of jobs and business opportunities. A booming tourism industry helps to build infrastructure such as roads, parks, hospitals, schools and community areas. It also helps to preserve heritage sites, natural wonders, and precious cultures, by creating space for people to showcase their cultural traditions and protect sacred areas. Your travels can have a direct positive impact when you stay in locally-owned accommodation, shop in artisan markets, take part in traditional festivals, and tour with local guides. The tourism industry also helps to protect the environment and its wildlife, with many tourism businesses offering eco-friendly services and encouraging tourists to respect the lands and communities they visit. Dozens of natural areas are gaining protection because of their importance to the tourism industry. There are also many inspiring cases of change, such as former poachers turning into safari guides or gamekeepers, as the income from tourists wanting to see wildlife means that protecting the animals is a far more valuable venture. Your trip can have a direct positive impact when you pay entry fees for national parks to ensure ongoing preservation. You should also always make sure you leave only footprints and take only photos from the natural areas you visit. These positive impacts of the tourism industry are all part of a move towards responsible tourism. It's all about having a beneficial effect on the communities we visit, protecting our wildlife, and caring for our planet.

Tourism is vital for the success of many economies around the world. There are several benefits of tourism on host destinations. Tourism boosts the revenue of the economy, creates thousands of jobs, develops the infrastructures of a country, and plants a sense of cultural exchange between foreigners and citizens. The number of jobs created by tourism in many different areas is significant. These jobs are not only a part of the tourism sector but may also include the agricultural sector, communication sector, health sector, and the educational sector. Many tourists travel to experience the hosting destination's culture, different traditions, and gastronomy. This is very profitable to local restaurants, shopping centers, and stores. Melbourne, Australia's population is greatly affected by tourism. It has a population of around 4 million people and around 22,000 citizens are employed by the tourism sector only. Governments that rely on tourism for a big percentage of their revenue invest a lot in the infrastructure of the country. They want more and more tourists to visit their country which means that safe and advanced facilities are necessary. This leads to new roads and highways, developed parks, improved public spaces, new airports, and possibly better schools and hospitals. Safe and innovative infrastructures allow for a smooth flow of goods and services. Moreover, local people experience an opportunity for economic and educational growth. Tourism creates a cultural exchange between tourists and local citizens. Exhibitions, conferences, and events usually attract foreigners. Organizing authorities usually gain profits

from registration fees, gift sales, exhibition spaces, and sales of media copyright. Furthermore, foreign tourists bring diversity and cultural enrichment to the hosting country. Tourism is a great opportunity for foreigners to learn about a new culture, but it also creates many opportunities for local citizens. It allows young entrepreneurs to establish new products and services that would not be sustainable on the local population of residents alone. Moreover, residents experience the benefits that come with tourism occurring in their own country.

The World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) has revealed a new report that outlined the vital role the industry will play in the U.S.' economic recovery post-COVID-19 (coronavirus) pandemic. In its annual Economic Impact Report (EIR), WTTC shared that in 2019 travel and tourism accounted for 8.6 percent of the total U.S. economy and approximately 16.8 million jobs, or 10.7 percent of the country's total workforce. The report also revealed international visitor spend totaled a \$195.1 billion, representing 7.8 percent of the U.S.' total exports. This was, in part, the WTTC says, driven by the success of the efforts of Brand USA, which promotes travel to the U.S. (Last year, following its success, the U.S. government reauthorized the tourism marketing organization through to 2027.) In addition, this continued success was also driven by a strong private sector and the excellent private-public coordination across states, destinations and at a country level, led by the U.S. This comprehensive report also shows the sheer size of the domestic travel market in the U.S, and how it will be key to powering the economic recovery. In 2019, domestic spending accounted for 84 percent of all spend, compared to 16 percent international in 2019. According to the report, leisure travel spending accounted for 70 percent, whilst business travel accounted for 30 percent. Gloria Guevara, WTTC president and CEO, said in an official release, "Our analysis underscores how vital travel and tourism will be in powering the recovery of the U.S. economy, generating new jobs and driving visitors back to the U.S., having a positive domino effect on suppliers large and small throughout the industry. The WTTC's EIR revealed Canada and Mexico accounted for 26 percent and 24 percent, respectively, of all visitors respectively to the U.S. between 2016 and 2018, with the U.K. following at 6 percent, Japan at 5 percent and China at 4 percent. The remainder of the globe comprised the last 35 percent.

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